

***Early Glucose and Insulin Dynamics During
Prolonged Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT)
Distinguish Reactive Hypoglycemia from Pseudo-Hypoglycemia***

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Abstract

Background. Reactive hypoglycemia (RH) is characterized by the occurrence of Whipple's triad within hours after carbohydrate ingestion, whereas pseudo-hypoglycemia (PH) involves hypoglycemic-like symptoms without pathological reductions in plasma glucose. Differentiating between these conditions is essential to avoid misdiagnosis and unnecessary testing.

Methods. We retrospectively analyzed 74 patients who underwent a prolonged oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) for suspected RH. RH was defined as plasma glucose <55 mg/dL between 180 and 300 minutes, and PH as hypoglycemic-like symptoms with glucose \geq 55 mg/dL at all time points. Clinical, glycemetic, and insulinemic parameters were compared between groups.

Results. 83% of the participants were women. Confirmed RH occurred in 26% of patients, and PH in 20%. All PH subjects reported symptoms, which were associated with higher nadir glucose levels (76 vs 50 mg/dL). Compared with PH patients, RH patients exhibited higher 1-hour glucose levels (146 vs 123 mg/dL), and a lower Matsuda index (5.7 vs 18.6). RH also showed greater Δ GLU0–1 (74 vs 34 mg/dL; $p = 0.003$) and greater Δ INS0–2 (63 vs 44 μ U/mL; $p = 0.047$). A higher proportion of RH had 1-hour glucose >155 mg/dL (44% vs 13%; $p = 0.045$). No differences were observed in age, sex, BMI, lipid profile, or baseline glycemia and insulin-sensitivity indices.

Conclusions. Dynamic OGTT parameters—particularly 1-hour glucose, and Matsuda index—distinguish RH from PH more effectively than nadir glucose alone. Incorporating these markers may enhance diagnostic accuracy and inform clinical decision-making, optimizing the use of OGTTs.

Keywords: Reactive hypoglycemia; Pseudo-hypoglycemia; Oral glucose tolerance test; Insulin sensitivity; Matsuda index.

Introduction

Reactive hypoglycemia (RH) is characterized by the occurrence of Whipple's triad following carbohydrate ingestion, typically within 3 to 5 hours after a meal [1]. It is a heterogeneous condition whose pathogenesis remains incompletely understood, particularly in individuals without predisposing factors such as a history of bariatric surgery [1]. However, it has been associated with dysregulated eating patterns, inappropriate insulin secretion, and insulin resistance [2,4]. Despite being commonly encountered in clinical practice, the definition and management of RH remain controversial, mainly due to the lack of widely accepted diagnostic criteria. Current guidelines, such as those from the Endocrine Society (ES) and the American Diabetes Association (ADA), do not recommend performing prolonged oral glucose tolerance tests (OGTTs) for the diagnosis of RH, due to their low specificity and high rate of false positives [5,6]. Alternatively, the Mixed Meal Tolerance Test (MMTT), mimicking patients' daily diet more physiologically, is suggested to evaluate glucose decline and coexisting hypoglycemic like symptoms [5,6]. However, the definition of MMTT remains unclear: there are no specific guidelines according to meal composition and measurement that should be conducted during postprandial period. Nevertheless, the prolonged OGTT remains widely used in real-world clinical settings, primarily due to its accessibility and logistical feasibility [5]. A particularly relevant issue in this context is pseudo-hypoglycemia (PH), also termed "alimentary syndrome," in which patients report symptoms suggestive of hypoglycemia despite the absence of a pathological reduction in plasma glucose levels, typically remaining above 70 mg/dL [7,8]. This phenomenon can lead to misinterpretation of test results, inaccurate diagnoses, and suboptimal clinical management [7]. To date, few studies have directly compared patients with confirmed RH during OGTT to those with PH. Identifying clinical or metabolic markers that can distinguish between these two conditions may help optimize patient selection for OGTT and improve the interpretation of its results [1,2,7]. The present study aimed to compare the clinical, glycemetic, and insulinemic characteristics of patients undergoing prolonged OGTT for suspected RH, distinguishing those who developed true hypoglycemia from those with PH, to identify potential predictive markers and rationalize the use of the test in clinical practice, particularly when the mixed meal test (MMT) is not available.

Methods

We retrospectively analyzed 74 consecutive patients who underwent a prolonged OGTT at the IRCCS Ospedale San Raffaele (Milan, Italy), between 2020 and 2024. Participants were referred for OGTT due to suspected RH based on reported hypoglycemic-like symptoms.

Inclusion criteria:

- Age ≥ 18 years
- History of postprandial symptoms consistent with hypoglycemia (e.g., palpitations, tremor, sweating, psychomotor agitation, nausea, hunger, or confusion)
- Availability of both glucose and insulin measurements during OGTT.

Exclusion criteria:

- Age <18 years
- Pregnancy or breastfeeding
- Renal or hepatic failure
- Diagnosis of any type of diabetes mellitus according to ADA/WHO criteria
- Endocrine (C-peptide <0.6 ng/mL) or exocrine pancreatic insufficiency
- Pancreatic neoplasms
- Diagnosis of Hirata disease (positive anti-insulin autoantibodies)
- History of bariatric surgery
- Use of insulin or other anti-diabetic hypoglycemic agents, or any pharmacologic treatment known to affect glucose tolerance or carbohydrate/lipid metabolism.

The OGTT was performed according to standard recommendations, with the administration of a 75-g anhydrous oral glucose solution and venous blood sampling every hour up to 300 minutes (T0, T60, T120, T180, T240, T300) for plasma glucose and insulin measurements.

Of the 74 patients undergoing a prolonged OGTT for suspected RH, only those fulfilling the criteria for either reactive hypoglycemia (RH) or pseudo-hypoglycemia (PH) were included in the present analysis.

Participants were categorized into two mutually exclusive groups:

- RH: plasma glucose <55 mg/dL between 180 and 300 minutes, regardless of the presence of symptoms. This choice was motivated by the small number of subjects with asymptomatic biochemical hypoglycemia and the aim of ensuring statistical homogeneity.
- PH: hypoglycemic-like symptoms with plasma glucose \geq 55 mg/dL at all time points during OGTT.

Patients with plasma glucose levels \geq 55 mg/dL and without hypoglycemia-like symptoms at all time points were excluded from the analysis.

For each participant, the following data were collected:

- Baseline parameters: age, sex, BMI, fasting plasma glucose and insulin, indices of insulin resistance (Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance [HOMA-IR], Triglyceride-Glucose Index [TyG-I], Quantitative Insulin Sensitivity Check Index [QUICKI]), fasting C-peptide, baseline glycemic status (euglycemia, impaired glucose tolerance, diabetes mellitus)
- Dynamic parameters: plasma glucose and insulin at each OGTT time point, Matsuda Index, glycemic status post-load (euglycemia, impaired glucose tolerance, diabetes mellitus)

Impaired fasting glucose (IFG), impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) and diabetes mellitus (DM) were defined according to ADA/WHO criteria.

A multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of reactive hypoglycemia.

Results

Baseline characteristics of the total study cohort are shown in Table 1. A total of 74 patients underwent a prolonged OGTT due to clinical suspicion of RH. The median age of the cohort was 45 years (IQR, 34-56 years), and the majority of participants were female, accounting for 83% of the total. The majority of patients (73%) complained about post-prandial hypoglycemic-like symptoms. 92% of patients reported neuroglycopenic symptoms and 53% of patients reported adrenergic symptoms. Only 19 patients (26%) had confirmatory evidence of hypoglycemia on home capillary glucose testing. 81% of patients were euglycemic, while 19% of them had IFG/IGT at baseline. 33 patients (45%) reported hypoglycemic-like symptoms during prolonged OGTT. Based on the study criteria, 33% of the patients had confirmed reactive hypoglycemia (RH), whereas 20% were classified as having PH. Among patients classified as RH, 72% had late hypoglycemia (between the 4th and 5th hour), while 18% had early hypoglycemia (within the 3rd hour). After oral glucose load, 16% of patients were diagnosed with impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) and only 6% with diabetes.

When comparing the two groups, several significant differences emerged (Table 2, Figure 1). Patients with RH exhibited higher plasma glucose concentrations at one hour after glucose loading, with a median value of 146 mg/dL compared to 123 mg/dL in the PH group ($p = 0.025$). Insulin sensitivity, as assessed by the Matsuda index, was markedly reduced in the RH group (median 5.7) compared with the PH group (median 18.6; $p = 0.036$). The glycemic excursion between baseline and the first hour ($\Delta\text{GLU0-1}$) was substantially greater in RH patients, with an increase of 74 mg/dL versus 34 mg/dL observed in PH patients ($p = 0.003$). Similarly, the insulin levels from baseline to the second hour ($\Delta\text{INS0-2}$) were more pronounced in the RH group, with an excursion of 63 $\mu\text{U/mL}$ compared to 44 $\mu\text{U/mL}$ in the PH group ($p = 0.047$). Moreover, a greater proportion of RH patients had a one-hour glucose value exceeding 155 mg/dL (44% versus 13%; $p = 0.045$). A non-significant trend was also found for one-hour glucose exceeding 209 mg/dL in patients with RH (20% vs 0%, $p = 0.064$).

Clinically, the proportion of patients experiencing symptoms during the OGTT was high in both groups, but reached 100% in the PH group, compared to 72% in the RH group ($p = 0.024$). Nevertheless, nadir glucose levels at five hours were significantly lower in patients with RH compared to PH (median 50mg/dl vs 76mg/dl, $p < 0.01$). In contrast, no significant differences were observed between the two groups in terms of age, sex distribution, body mass index, lipid profile, indices of basal insulin resistance or baseline and post-load glycemic status (IGT/DM)

In a stepwise multivariate logistic regression adjusted for sex and BMI, including only variables significant at univariate analysis, the $\Delta\text{GLU0-1}$ was independently associated with the risk of RH (OR 1.69, $p = 0.041$; Table 3).

These findings suggest that dynamic glucose and insulin patterns during prolonged OGTT can provide meaningful discrimination between RH and PH, despite similarities in baseline clinical and metabolic characteristics.

Discussion

Our results support the notion that patients with confirmed RH exhibit a distinct glycemic–insulinemic profile compared to those with PH, characterized by a pronounced glucose peak at 1 hour, followed by a significant decline at 5 hours, and a notably lower Matsuda index—indicative of reduced dynamic insulin sensitivity [1,2]. This aligns with the understanding that insulin resistance plays a central role in this condition, especially in individuals with overweight or obesity, as supported by recent insights into molecular mediators, such as oxidative stress and adipose-derived inflammatory signals, that drive insulin resistance [3,4]. The pathophysiological mechanism we observed, characterized by an early glucose surge followed by a delayed yet exaggerated insulin response, echoes models describing impaired first-phase insulin secretion, followed by a hyperactive second phase, ultimately leading to late postprandial hypoglycemia [1,9]. In contrast, PH patients—who experience hypoglycemic symptoms without actual hypoglycemia—reflect the clinical definition of PH, where symptoms occur despite plasma glucose levels >70 mg/dL, often related to psychosomatic factors or emotional dysregulation [7,8,10]. Behavioral contributions are also relevant: recent findings in individuals with binge-eating disorder (BED) or food addiction (FA) showed a high rate—up to 28%—of RH episodes during extended 5-hour OGTTs, emphasizing a behavioral–metabolic interaction [8]. This is highly relevant in clinical practice: in our cohort, the majority of patients were referred for testing based mostly on reported symptoms, yet only 26% had confirmatory evidence of hypoglycemia on home capillary glucose measurements. This underscores the importance of careful patient selection to avoid unnecessary testing, misdiagnosis, and potential overtreatment [11].

From a diagnostic perspective, our findings also highlight the limitation of the prolonged OGTT: more than one in five patients with a clinical suspicion of RH were ultimately classified as PH. This confirms the low specificity of the test when interpreted solely on the basis of the nadir glucose value [5].

One-hour post-load glucose (1hPG) has emerged in the last decade as a new marker of cardio-metabolic risk. Several longitudinal studies have demonstrated that elevated 1hPG during the OGTT, even in individuals with normal glucose tolerance, is associated with a significantly higher risk of progression to prediabetes and type 2 diabetes, as well as with an increased incidence of cardiovascular events. This association appears to be independent of fasting and 2-hour post-load glucose levels, suggesting that 1hPG captures early alterations in glucose and lipid metabolism and vascular health that may precede conventional diagnostic thresholds [12-17].

More recent evidence has strengthened these findings. A 2025 analysis from the San Antonio Heart Study identified 1hPG as the strongest predictor of prediabetes progression, proposing a cut-off between 120 and 155

mg/dL to define a “pre-prediabetes” category characterized by marked insulin resistance and an adverse metabolic profile [18]. In line with this evidence, the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) recently recommended using 1hPG to detect early dysglycemia, with thresholds of ≥ 155 mg/dL for intermediate hyperglycemia (IFG/IGT) and ≥ 209 mg/dL for type 2 diabetes, with confirmatory testing advised before establishing the diagnosis [19]. Interestingly, in our cohort, a significantly higher proportion of patients with RH exhibited a 1hPG greater than 155mg/dl compared to PH. Although the relationship between RH and dysregulated glucose metabolism is not fully understood, RH has been hypothesized as a pre-diabetic state on the basis of shared pathophysiological mechanisms, namely deficient first phase insulin secretion, compensatory hyperinsulinemic response, insulin-resistance and incretin dysregulation [20]. However, a prospective study of 39 adult women with RH showed no increased incidence of DM at six years of follow-up [21]. Consistently, in our cohort, the prevalence of IGT/DM based on OGTT criteria was comparable between RH and PH. Nevertheless, longitudinal studies that have specifically evaluated the evolution of glucose tolerance in individuals with RH are lacking. This discrepancy likely reflects the heterogeneity of RH phenotypes, manifesting with different patterns, each one driven by a different pathophysiologic basis and carrying a different risk of progression towards impaired glucose tolerance [20]. Specifically, while idiopathic RH (occurring within the 3rd hour) has been associated with increased insulin sensitivity, late RH (occurring at the 3rd - 5th hour) is driven by inhibition of first-phase insulin secretion and insulin-resistance [22] and has been suggested to represent a predictor of diabetes [20, 22]. On the basis of these findings, it can be hypothesized that patients with RH may already exhibit subtle pre-clinical alterations in glucose regulation, not detectable through baseline glyco-metabolic parameters, but unmasked by dynamic testing, yet not sufficient to result in overt IGT or diabetes.

Collectively, these data underscore the need for a diagnostic paradigm that goes beyond measuring the nadir glucose. Incorporating dynamic markers—such as a 1-hour glucose level and dynamic insulin sensitivity indices—could enhance differentiation between RH and PH, allow clinicians to discontinue the test in low-risk individuals, reduce misdiagnoses, and guide more precise clinical management [5, 6, 23].

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, its retrospective and single-center design may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader populations. Second, although the sample size is sufficient for the statistical analyses performed, it remains relatively small, which may limit the power to detect more subtle differences between groups. Third, patient selection was based on clinical suspicion of RH, which could introduce referral bias and overrepresent certain phenotypes. Fourth, no long-term follow-up data were available to assess the clinical evolution of either RH or PH, including potential progression to dysglycemia or type 2 diabetes (T2D). Finally, additional hormonal parameters potentially relevant to postprandial glucose regulation—such as incretin hormones or counterregulatory responses—were not assessed, which might have provided further insights into the underlying pathophysiology.

Conclusion

In this study, a prolonged OGTT proved to be a useful tool for distinguishing RH from PH when interpreted in the context of dynamic glycemetic and insulinemic responses, rather than just the nadir glucose level. RH was characterized by higher 1-hour glucose levels and reduced insulin sensitivity, whereas PH presented with stable glucose patterns despite symptom reporting. These findings suggest that incorporating parameters such as a 1-hour glucose level, the Matsuda index, and insulin delta values into the diagnostic process can enhance accuracy and reduce misclassification. Furthermore, recognizing the behavioral and psychosomatic dimensions of PH and the potential cardiometabolic implications of RH in insulin-resistant individuals underscores the need for a multidimensional diagnostic framework. Future research should validate these markers prospectively and assess whether targeted lifestyle or pharmacologic interventions can mitigate both symptomatic burden and long-term metabolic risk in patients with RH.

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Data availability

The dataset generated and analyzed during the current study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. All data is stored in a password-protected database. The dataset has been pseudo-anonymized and does not contain any direct or indirect identifiers that could allow the re-identification of individual patients (e.g., only age is reported instead of date of birth).

Ethical approval

All data were retrieved from the OSR digital medical record system and stored in a password-protected, pseudo-anonymized database in compliance with the Italian Medicines Agency (AIFA) regulations (aligned with the Ministerial Decree of November 30, 2021 – Article 6, Paragraph 3, and within the framework of national regulations implementing Regulation (EU) No. 536/2014), and with the guidelines of the OSR Ethics Committee (OSR EC, “Comitato Etico Territoriale Lombardia 1”, Via Olgettina 60 - 20132 Milano, established under “Deliberazione Regione Lombardia n° XII / 281” of 15/05/2023). All patients signed informed consent prior to participation, and the study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: A.V., F.V.; Data curation: A.V., F.V.; Writing – original draft: A.V., M.A.; Writing – review & editing: A.V., M.A., F.V.; Visualization: M.A.; Approval of final manuscript: All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the total cohort

	Total cohort (n.74)
Age, years	45 (34-56)
Males/Females	11/63 (17%/83%)
BMI, kg/m ²	25 (21.8-27.9)
Familial history of DM	31 (42%)
Fasting symptoms	33 (45%)
Post prandial symptoms	53 (72%)
Types of symptoms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adrenergic • Neuroglycopenic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 43 (58%) • 68 (92%)
Hypoglycemia on home capillary glucose testing	19 (26%)
Baseline glycemic status: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Euglycemia • IFG/IGT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60 (81%) • 14 (19%)
HbA1c	33.5 (31-37.7)
Total cholesterol, mg/dl	189 (160-211)
HDL-c, mg/dl	57 (49-73)
Triglycerides, mg/dl	84 (56-106)
LDL-c, mg/dl	102 (83-127)
TyG index	4.48 (4.23-4.55)
Fasting glucose, mg/dl	85 (79-93)
Fasting insulin, μ U/mL	7.5 (5-12)

HOMA-IR	1.55 (1-2.7)
QUICKI	0.356 (0.330-0.387)
Fasting C-peptide, ng/ml	1.69 (1.54-2.41)
Symptoms during OGTT	33 (45%)
Reactive Hypoglycemia (RH)	25 (34%)
Type of RH:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early (within the 3rd hour) • Late (3rd - 5th hour) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 (28%) • 18 (72%)
Pseudohypoglycemia (PH)	15 (20%)
Post OGTT glycemc status	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Euglycemia • IGT • DM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 58 (78%) • 12 (16%) • 4 (6%)

Legend. BMI = body mass index; DM = diabetes mellitus; IFG = impaired fasting glucose; IGT = impaired glucose tolerance; HbA1c =glycosylated hemoglobin; HDL-c = high density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-c = low density lipoprotein cholesterol; TyG index = triglyceride-glucose index; HOMA-I = Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance; QUICKI = Quantitative Insulin Sensitivity Check Index; OGTT = oral glucose tolerance test.

Table 2. Baseline and post- oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) characteristics of patients with RH compared to PH

	RH (n.25)	PH (n.15)	P value
Age, years	43 (35-60)	39 (34-50)	0.394
Males/Females	1/24 (4%/96%)	3/12 (20%/80%)	0.102
BMI, kg/m ²	24 (20-28.3)	25.9 (24.2-27.9)	0.321
Familial history of DM	13 (52%)	8 (53%)	0.935
Fasting symptoms	10 (40%)	6 (40%)	>0.99
Post prandial symptoms	17 (68%)	13 (87%)	0.187
Types of symptoms:			
• Adrenergic	• 14 (56%)	• 12 (80%)	• 0.123
• Neuroglycopenic	• 22 (88%)	• 14 (93%)	• 0.586
Hypoglycemia on home capillary glucose testing	9 (36%)	2 (13%)	0.120
Baseline glycemc status:			
• Euglycemia	• 19 (76%)	• 12 (80%)	0.769
• IFG/IGT	• 6 (24%)	• 3 (20%)	
HbA1c, mmol/mol	34 (33-38)	33 (31-36)	0.505
Total cholesterol, mg/dl	182 (160-198)	193 (158-210)	0.793
HDL-c, mg/dl	60 (52-73)	70 (52-84)	0.664
Triglycerides, mg/dl	78 (48-92)	93 (80-104)	0.188
LDL, mg/dl	95 (79-118)	99 (96-109)	0.504
TyG index	4.4 (4.2-4.54)	4.5 (4.43-4.54)	0.349

Fasting glucose, mg/dl	82 (76-94)	85 (80-93)	0.234
Fasting insulin, μ U/mL	6.8 (5.4-12)	10.1 (7.8-12)	0.308
HOMA-IR	1.27 (1.1-2.7)	2.14 (1.7-2.67)	0.230
QUICKI	0.370 (0.330-0.380)	0.340 (0.330-0.350)	0.144
Symptoms during OGTT	18 (72%)	15 (100%)	0.024
Post OGTT glycemic status			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Euglycemia • IGT • DM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 17 (68%) • 6 (24%) • 2 (8%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 (80%) • 2 (13%) • 1 (7%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.410 • 0.414 • 0.877
1-hour glucose >155 mg/dl	11 (44%)	2 (13%)	0.045
1-hour glucose >209 mg/dl	5 (20%)	0 (0%)	0.064

Legend. RH = reactive hypoglycemia; PH = pseudohypoglycemia; BMI = body mass index; DM = diabetes mellitus; IFG = impaired fasting glucose; IGT = impaired glucose tolerance; HbA1c = glycosylated hemoglobin; HDL-c = high density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-c = low density lipoprotein cholesterol; TyG index = triglyceride-glucose index; HOMA-I = Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance; QUICKI = Quantitative Insulin Sensitivity Check Index; OGTT = oral glucose tolerance test.

Figure 1. Glucose and insulin profiles during prolonged oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) in reactive hypoglycemia (RH) and pseudo-hypoglycemia (PH) patients.

Legend. Plasma glucose (left axis, red lines) and serum insulin (right axis, blue lines) concentrations during a 300-minute oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) in patients with reactive hypoglycemia (RH, solid lines) and pseudo-hypoglycemia (PH, dashed lines). Data represent median values at baseline (0 minutes) and at 60, 120, 180, 240, and 300 minutes after ingestion of 75 g of oral glucose. RH patients showed higher 1-hour glucose peaks and a higher insulin levels excursion from baseline to the second hour; with a greater subsequent glucose decline, and lower dynamic insulin sensitivity compared to PH patients.

Table 3. Multivariate logistic regression for independent predictors of reactive hypoglycemia (RH)

	Odds ratio (C.I 95%)	p
1 hour-glucose	0.65 (0.42-1)	0.051
Δ GLU0-1	1.69 (1.02-2.81)	0.041
Δ INS0-2	1.04 (0.98-1.10)	0.127
Matsuda Index	1.01 (0.95-1.08)	0.625

Legend. Δ GLU0-1= glycemic excursion between baseline and the first hour; Δ INS0-2 insulinemic excursion between baseline and the first hour.

References

1. Lv, X., et al. (2020). Identification of reactive hypoglycemia with different basic BMI and its causes by prolonged oral glucose tolerance test. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity*, 13, 4717–4726. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S280084>
2. Mert, A. (2023). *Association of reactive hypoglycemia with early β -cell dysfunction and insulin resistance*. *Ankara Medical Journal*, (1), 49–60. <https://doi.org/10.5505/amj.2023.22844>
3. Kościuszko, M., et al. (2024). Assessing the impact of body composition, metabolic and oxidative stress parameters on insulin resistance as a prognostic marker for reactive hypoglycemia: a cross-sectional study in overweight, obese, and normal weight individuals. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 15, 1329802. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2024.1329802>
Open-access: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11035812/>
4. Li, M. (2022). *Trends in insulin resistance: insights into mechanisms and implications for metabolic disease*. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*, 7, 73. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-022-01073-0>
5. Dey, A. K., et al., DGENius Group. (2024). Expert consensus recommendations on the evaluation and management of hypoglycemia in diabetes. *Journal of Diabetology*, 15(1), 38–62. https://doi.org/10.4103/jod.jod_121_23
6. Cryer PE, Axelrod L, Grossman AB, Heller SR, Montori VM, Seaquist ER, Service FJ; Endocrine Society. Evaluation and management of adult hypoglycemic disorders: an Endocrine Society Clinical Practice Guideline. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2009 Mar;94(3):709-28. doi: 10.1210/jc.2008-1410. Epub 2008 Dec 16. PMID: 19088155.
7. Rania, M., et al. (2023). *Reactive hypoglycemia in binge-eating disorder and food addiction during a 5-h OGTT*. *Journal of Eating Disorders*, 11(1), 112. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40337-023-00891-z>
8. Di Giuseppe, G., et al. (2023). First-phase insulin secretion: can its evaluation direct therapeutic approaches? *Trends in Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 34(4), 216–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tem.2023.02.001>
9. Mathew, P., & Thoppil, D. (2025). Hypoglycemia. In StatPearls. StatPearls Publishing. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK534841/>
10. Chalew SA, Koetter H, Hoffman S, Levin PA, Kowarski AA. Diagnosis of reactive hypoglycemia: pitfalls in the use of the oral glucose tolerance test. *South Med J*. 1986 Mar;79(3):285-7. doi: 10.1097/00007611-198603000-00006. PMID: 3952536.
11. Abdul-Ghani MA, Lyssenko V, Tuomi T, DeFronzo RA, Groop L. Fasting versus postload plasma glucose concentration and the risk for future type 2 diabetes: results from the Botnia Study. *Diabetes Care*. 2009 Feb;32(2):281-6. doi: 10.2337/dc08-1264. Epub 2008 Nov 18. PMID: 19017778; PMCID: PMC2628694.
12. Marini MA, Succurro E, Frontoni S, Mastroianni S, Arturi F, Sciacqua A, Lauro R, Hribal ML, Perticone F, Sesti G. Insulin sensitivity, β -cell function, and incretin effect in individuals with elevated 1-h post-load plasma glucose levels. *Diabetes Care*. 2012;35(4):868–872. doi:10.2337/dc11-2181
13. Succurro E, Marini MA, Arturi F, Grembiale A, Lugarà M, Andreozzi F, Sciacqua A, Lauro R, Hribal ML, Perticone F, Sesti G. Elevated one-hour post-load plasma glucose levels identifies subjects with

- normal glucose tolerance but early carotid atherosclerosis. *Atherosclerosis*. 2009 Nov;207(1):245-9. doi: [10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2009.04.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2009.04.006). Epub 2009 Apr 11. PMID: 19410252.
14. Nakagomi A, Sunami Y, Okada S, Ohno Y, Shoji T, Fujisawa T, Kobayashi Y. Association between 1-h post-load plasma glucose levels and arterial stiffness in normotensive subjects with normal glucose tolerance. *Diab Vasc Dis Res*. 2018 Jan;15(1):39-45. doi: [10.1177/1479164117736509](https://doi.org/10.1177/1479164117736509). Epub 2017 Oct 28. PMID: 29081239.
 15. Liang K, Wang J, Yang Z, Gong Q, Zhang J, Shao R. Atherogenic lipid parameters in people with normal glucose tolerance: implications from elevated 1-hour post-load plasma glucose. *Cardiovasc Diabetol*. 2025 May 14;24(1):207. doi: [10.1186/s12933-025-02722-8](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12933-025-02722-8). PMID: 40369580; PMCID: PMC12079842.
 16. Andreozzi F, Mannino GC, Perticone M, Perticone F, Sesti G. Elevated 1-h post-load plasma glucose levels in subjects with normal glucose tolerance are associated with a pro-atherogenic lipid profile. *Atherosclerosis*. 2017 Jan;256:15-20. doi: [10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2016.11.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2016.11.020). Epub 2016 Nov 17. PMID: 27940375.
 17. Abdul-Ghani M, Abu-Farha M, Abdul-Ghani T, Chavez-Velazquez A, Merovci A, DeFronzo RA, Alajmi F, Stern M, Al-Mulla F. One-Hour Plasma Glucose Predicts the Progression From Normal Glucose Tolerance to Prediabetes. *Diabetes Care*. 2025 May 16;dc242832. doi: [10.2337/dc24-2832](https://doi.org/10.2337/dc24-2832). Epub ahead of print. PMID: 40377532.
 18. Bergman M, Manco M, Satman I, Chan J, Schmidt MI, Sesti G, Vanessa Fiorentino T, Abdul-Ghani M, Jagannathan R, Kumar Thyparambil Aravindakshan P, Gabriel R, Mohan V, Buysschaert M, Bennakhi A, Pascal Kengne A, Dorcelly B, Nilsson PM, Tuomi T, Battelino T, Hussain A, Ceriello A, Tuomilehto J. International Diabetes Federation Position Statement on the 1-hour post-load plasma glucose for the diagnosis of intermediate hyperglycaemia and type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*. 2024 Mar; 209:111589. doi: [10.1016/j.diabres.2024.111589](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diabres.2024.111589). Epub 2024 Mar 7. PMID: 38458916.
 19. Altuntaş Y. Postprandial Reactive Hypoglycemia. *Sisli Etfal Hastan Tip Bul*. 2019 Aug 28;53(3):215-220. doi: [10.14744/SEMB.2019.59455](https://doi.org/10.14744/SEMB.2019.59455). PMID: 32377086; PMCID: PMC7192270
 20. Volčanšek Š, Rahne Perc U, Lunder M, Pongrac Barlovič D. No Indices of Increased Type 2 Diabetes Risk in Individuals with Reactive Postprandial Hypoglycemia. *Metabolites*. 2022 Dec 8;12(12):1232. doi: [10.3390/metabo12121232](https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo12121232). PMID: 36557270; PMCID: PMC9787184.
 21. Tamburrano G, Leonetti F, Sbraccia P, Giaccari A, Locuratolo N, Lala A. Increased insulin sensitivity in patients with idiopathic reactive hypoglycemia. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 1989 Oct;69(4):885-90. doi: [10.1210/jcem-69-4-885](https://doi.org/10.1210/jcem-69-4-885). PMID: 2674188.

22. Altuntas Y, Bilir M, Ucak S, Gundogdu S. Reactive hypoglycemia in lean young women with PCOS and correlations with insulin sensitivity and with beta cell function. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2005 Apr 1;119(2):198-205. doi: [10.1016/j.ejogrb.2004.07.038](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2004.07.038). PMID: 15808380.
23. Younes YR, Cron N, Field BCT, Nayyar V, Clark J, Zachariah S, Lakshmipathy K, Isuga JO, Maghsoodi N, Emmanuel J. Proposed treatment strategy for reactive hypoglycaemia. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).* 2024 Feb 2;15:1332702. doi: [10.3389/fendo.2024.1332702](https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2024.1332702). PMID: 38370356; PMCID: PMC10869498.